

THE ESTIMATION OF VITAMIN C IN FOODSTUFFS.

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The previous method of estimating ascorbic acid in foodstuffs after heating the aqueous suspensions in H_2S (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **15**, 95) has been modified by the introduction of treatment with ascorbic acid oxidase, which appears to give more accurate values for "total, true" ascorbic acid. Values obtained by this method are higher than those obtained by the Tillmans-Harris method. The stability of ascorbic acid oxidase has been investigated.

The simple trichloroacetic acid extraction method has been extensively employed for the estimation of vitamin C in foodstuffs by titration with 2 : 6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. Along with vitamin C in plant foodstuffs, the enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase, has been found to be widely distributed (Chakraborty and Guha, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, **24**, 839). This enzyme is capable of oxidising ascorbic acid into the reversibly oxidised form (dehydroascorbic acid) when the plant tissue is disintegrated. If the grinding of the tissue is carried out under trichloroacetic acid, the action of the oxidase is minimised but not wholly suppressed. The amount of ascorbic acid which is thus oxidised cannot reduce the dye but is biologically potent. The simple Tillmans-Harris method, therefore, would tend to give a value for total ascorbic acid, which is a little too low. At the same time, evidence has been given (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 496) pointing to the presence of combined ascorbic acid or ascorbigen in several plant tissues, which is biologically potent but would not reduce the dye unless split up by heating. Thus the estimation of total ascorbic acid should include (a) the free ascorbic acid, (b) the dehydroascorbic acid which may be formed by the action of the oxidase, and (c) ascorbigen, if any. We, therefore, described in a previous paper (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **15**, 95) a method involving the heating of an aqueous suspension of the tissue in H_2S , so as to reduce the dehydroascorbic acid and split up ascorbigen, followed by titration against the indophenol indicator, so as to get the value of the total ascorbic acid.

The question, however, arises whether all the reducing material produced by heating in H_2S is ascorbic acid. This may be investigated by

using van Eekelen's method (Emmerie and van Eekelen, *Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 1153) to remove interfering substances. But we have found in unpublished experiments that if known quantities of ascorbic acid are added to extracts of several varieties of foodstuff, like cabbage, onion, guava and *patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica*), van Eekelen's method enables only about 60-75 per cent of the added ascorbic acid to be estimated. This shows that, while eliminating interfering substances, mercuric acetate at the same time causes some loss of ascorbic acid. But, even if van Eekelen's method is applied to cabbage and *patol* after H_2S treatment in the hot and in the cold, a difference is obtained in the reducing value (Sen-Gupta and Guha, 1939, *loc. cit.*). Thus, although van Eekelen's method involves some loss of ascorbic acid, the application of this method also shows that heat produces some reducing substance, which, as we have shown earlier (Sen-Gupta and Guha, 1939, *loc. cit.*), consists largely of ascorbic acid as tested with ascorbic acid oxidase. Part of the reducing substances produced by heating in H_2S , however, is non-specific. It is, therefore, apparent that the previous method for the estimation of ascorbic acid by heating an aqueous suspension of the foodstuff in H_2S (Sen-Gupta and Guha, 1937, *loc. cit.*) would give rather high values for ascorbic acid. The method has, therefore, been modified by introducing the action of ascorbic acid oxidase after treatment with H_2S in the hot condition. A preliminary note on the subject has been published elsewhere (Sen-Gupta and Guha, *Science and Culture*, 1938 3, 398).

The ascorbic acid oxidase has been prepared both from cucumber and white gourd (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 725) and its stability investigated under different conditions of storage. This information is necessary if the oxidase is to be used as a reagent for routine determination of vitamin C. Biological experiments are in progress to see how far the values obtained by this method agree with those obtained biologically.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ascorbic acid oxidase was prepared for these experiments from cucumber by the method of Tauber *et al.* (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, 110, 271; see also Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, *loc. cit.*) and purified by precipitating twice from aqueous solution by acetone. The oxidase preparation takes some time to dissolve in water.

The following plant foodstuffs were investigated—cabbage, *patol* (*Trichosanthes dioica*) and onion. All of them were treated in a similar

way. The same sampled foodstuff was taken for each of the following experiments.

(a) 10 G. were extracted with trichloroacetic acid in the usual way (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 30). An aliquot was titrated against the indophenol indicator and another aliquot titrated after treatment with ascorbic acid oxidase.

(b) 10 G. were disintegrated, suspended in 50 c.c. of water and treated with H_2S for 30 minutes. H_2S was removed in a current of CO_2 or N_2 and then the mixture was treated with 2.5 c.c. of 20 per cent trichloroacetic acid. After centrifugation the volume was made up to 100 c.c., aliquots of which were titrated severally before and after oxidase treatment.

(c) 10 G. were disintegrated, suspended in 50 c.c. of water, treated with H_2S for 15 minutes in the cold and then heated for 15 minutes in H_2S on the water-bath. After removal of H_2S by a current of CO_2 or N_2 the mixture was treated as under (b).

In all the methods (a), (b) and (c), the amount of reducing substance, which disappeared on oxidase treatment, gave the value for "true" ascorbic acid.

The treatment with the oxidase in each case was carried out in the following way. The p_H of the solution (usually 10 c.c.) was brought to 5.6 by the addition of a drop or two of NaOH. 2 C.c. of M-acetate buffer (p_H 5.6) and 3 c.c. of the enzyme solution (whose potency had been previously determined with pure ascorbic acid)* were added and the contents incubated at 40° for 30 minutes. The solution was made up to a definite volume and titrated against the dye. The difference in the dye value before and after incubation with the oxidase gave the measure of "true" ascorbic acid. The results are given in Table I, which shows that with these foodstuffs hot H_2S treatment gave a higher value for "true" ascorbic acid than by simple trichloroacetic acid treatment or by cold H_2S treatment.

* It is highly important that the amount of oxidase used should be more than sufficient to oxidise all the ascorbic acid likely to be present in the tissue extract. 3 C.c. of the present oxidase preparation were capable of oxidising 0.4 mg. of ascorbic acid under our conditions of experiment. The aliquots of the tissue extracts were, therefore, so chosen that they contained 0.3 mg. or less of reducing substance.

TABLE I.

(Mg. of ascorbic acid per 10 g. of foodstuff.)

Expt. No.	Foodstuff investigated.	Total reducing substances initially present			Reducing substances remaining after oxidase treatment			"Total, true" ascorbic acid		
		(a).	(b).	(c).	(a)	(b).	(c).	(a).	(b).	(c).
1	Cabbage	1.060	4.952	6.630	0.340	2.280	2.540	0.720	2.670	4.090
2	Cabbage	2.080	4.330	5.200	0.600	1.830	2.540	1.480	2.500	2.660
3	Patol (<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>)	1.130	2.476	2.971	0.000	1.200	1.300	1.130	1.276	1.671
4	Patol	1.223	3.058	3.466	0.000	1.240	1.300	1.223	1.818	2.166
5	Onion	1.040	1.543	1.654	0.000	0.000	0.000	1.040	1.543	1.654
6	Onion	0.945	1.300	1.567	0.307	0.594	0.940	0.638	0.706	0.726

(a) Simple trichloroacetic acid extraction.

(b) H₂S treatment in cold condition.(c) H₂S treatment in hot condition.

*The Application of the Present Method to the Estimation of
"total, true" Ascorbic Acid in Foodstuffs.*

Since the method given under (c) above appears to give higher values for true ascorbic acid than the ordinary procedure, it has been applied as a routine method of estimation to a number of other foodstuffs. The values obtained by simple trichloroacetic acid treatment in the ordinary way and also after oxidase treatment are given for comparison. The results are shown in Table II.

Stability of the Oxidase prepared from Cucumber.

As the method described above under (c) would require ascorbic acid oxidase as a regular reagent of known potency, it was considered desirable to investigate the stability of the oxidase under the following conditions of storage.

(1) The dry oxidase preparation was preserved in a vacuum desiccator at room temperature (27-30°) and also at 8-10°.

TABLE II.

No.	Bengali name.	English name.	Botanical name.	Mg. of ascorbic acid per 100 g. of foodstuffs.	Trichloroacetic acid extraction and oxidase treatment.	Hot H ₂ S and oxidase treatment. (present method).
				Simple trichloroacetic acid extraction.		
1	Kancha lanka	Green chillies	<i>Capiscus indicus</i>	50.0	50.0	68.9
2	Fulkopi	Cauliflower	<i>Brassica oleracea</i> Var. <i>botrytis</i>	50.0	50.0	62.6
3	Begoon	Brinjal	<i>Solenum melongena</i>	4.7	4.7	5.7
4	Mula	Radish	<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	20.8	20.8	23.4
5	—	Soya bean	—	1.0	1.0	1.1
6	Anarash	Pine apple	<i>Ananas sativa</i>	69.3	69.3	73.7
7	Pepe	Papaya	<i>Carica papaya</i>	65.0	65.0	75.2
8	Kala	Plantain (ripe)	<i>Musa sapientum</i>	4.6	4.6	12.1
9	Kala	" (green)	"	9.5	9.5	14.5
10	Dalim	Pomegranate	<i>Punica granatum</i>	50.0	49.1	52.2
11	Bel	Wood apple	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	86.7	60.4	61.9
12	Palang saak	Spinach	<i>Spinach oleracea</i>	14.9	14.9	52.0
13	Puin shak	—	<i>Bassela cardifolia</i>	41.6	41.6	89.3
14	Kalmi shak	Ipomoea	<i>Ipomoea reptans</i>	26.0	13.6	30.9
15	Matarshuti	Peas	<i>Pisum sativum</i>	19.8	19.8	23.1
16	Tomato	Tomato	<i>Lycopersicum esculentum</i>	27.3	27.3	39.6
17	Shalgom	Turnip	<i>Brassica campestris</i> Var.	22.1	22.1	31.8
18	Chalkumro	White gourd	<i>Benincasacriapra</i>	9.5	9.5	22.2
19	Sasha	Cucumber	<i>Cucumis sativas</i>	9.5	9.5	14.9
20	Batapi lebu	Shaddock	<i>Citrus decumana</i>	26.0	26.0	27.7
21	Apel	Apple	<i>Pyrus molas</i>	4.6	4.6	4.8
22	Am	Mango	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	6.5	6.5	12.0
23	Angur	Grapes	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>	5.5	2.4	3.6
24	Mocha	—	—	115.6	115.6	149.7
25	Shim	Bean	—	7.0	2.3	19.5
26	Kul (Narkel)	—	—	46.2	46.2	62.7
27	Kumra	Pumpkin	—	3.0	2.5	6.5
28	Shakalu	—	—	20.8	20.8	24.7
29	Kamla lebu	Orange	<i>Citrus aurantium</i>	30.6	30.6	31.4
30	Lebu	Lemon	<i>Citrus medica</i>	36.1	36.1	36.1

(2) The dry preparation was stored in ordinary colourless and amber coloured stoppered bottles at both room temperature and 8-10°.

(3) Aqueous solutions of the enzyme of definite concentrations were preserved with a drop or two of toluene in colourless and amber-coloured stoppered bottles at 8-10°.

The activity of the enzyme was investigated initially and after intervals of 2, 7 and 15 days. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

The dry enzyme preparation (0.05 g.) was dissolved in 16 c. c. of water and 3 c.c. of the enzyme solution were employed for the estimation of this activity.

State of material.	Conditions of storage.	Activity of the enzyme solutions (3 c.c.) measured in terms of ascorbic acid (mg.) oxidised under specified condition.			
		Initial.	After 2 days.	After 7 days.	After 15 days.
Dry powder	Vacuum desiccator at 8-10°	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.4	0.2
"	Vacuum desiccator at room temperature (27-30°)	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.4	0.2
"	Colourless bottle at 8-10°	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.3	0.2
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.4	—
"	Colourless bottle at room temperature (27-30°)	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.3	0.1
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.4	0.1
"	Amber-coloured bottle at room temperature (27-30°)	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.3	0.1
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.4	0.1
Aqueous solution	Colourless bottle at 8-10°	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.2	0.1
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.3	0.1
"	Amber-coloured bottle at 8-10°	(1) 0.4	0.4	0.2	0.1
		(2) 0.6	0.5	0.3	0.1

DISCUSSION

The previous method (Sen-Gupta and Guha, 1937, *loc. cit.*) for the estimation of total ascorbic acid in foodstuffs has been modified. The method now consists in heating an aqueous suspension of the foodstuff in H₂S and in titrating (after removal of H₂S by CO₂ or N₂) the solution, before and after treatment with ascorbic acid oxidase of known potency,

against 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. The method is described under (c). It appears to give the value for "total, true" ascorbic acid comprising free ascorbic acid, dehydroascorbic acid and ascorbigen, if any. The method has been applied to a number of foodstuffs and the results show that in most cases the values obtained are appreciably higher than those obtained by the usual method of trichloroacetic acid extraction. Biological experiments to check these results are in progress.

As ascorbic acid oxidase preparation would be a routine reagent in this method, its stability has been investigated under different conditions of storage. Colourless and coloured bottles do not seem to make any difference. The enzyme progressively deteriorates both in the dry state and in aqueous solution, but more rapidly in the latter state. A dry preparation of the enzyme is recommended to be used for periods not exceeding 7 days and aqueous solutions for periods not exceeding 3 days.

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